

Formal Axioms

Id	Axioms	Descriptive logic (Predicate)	DL Query (Prot.g.)
A1	A CommunitySmell is associated with at least one Cause which, if not properly managed, leads to Social Debt.	$(\text{CommunicationCause} \sqcup \text{CoordinationCause} \sqcup \text{CongruenceCause} \sqcup \text{CollaborationCause} \sqcup \text{AdministrativeCause}) \sqsubseteq \exists \text{cause CommunitySmell.xsd:string}$	$(\text{CommunicationCause} \text{ or } \text{CoordinationCause} \text{ or } \text{CongruenceCause} \text{ or } \text{CollaborationCause} \text{ or } \text{'Administrative cause'}) \text{ and } (\text{'Cause Community Smell'} \text{ some } \text{xsd:string})$
A2	A Cause linked to a specific Socio-technical Factor contributes to the emergence of Social Debt that affects that same factor; furthermore, it must be covered by at least one preventive Strategy applicable to the factor.	$(\text{CoordinationCause} \sqcup \text{CommunicationCause} \sqcup \text{CongruenceCause} \sqcup \text{CollaborationCause} \sqcup \text{AdministrativeCause}) \sqsubseteq (\exists \text{hasCoordinationStrategy.CoordinationStrategy} \sqcup \exists \text{hasCollaborationStrategy.CollaborationStrategy} \sqcup \exists \text{hasCongruenceStrategy.CongruenceStrategy} \sqcup \exists \text{hasCommunicationStrategy.CommunicationStrategy} \sqcup \exists \text{hasAdministrativePreventiveStrategy.AdministrativePreventiveStrategy})$	$(\text{CoordinationCause} \text{ or } \text{CommunicationCause} \text{ or } \text{CongruenceCause} \text{ or } \text{'Administrative cause'} \text{ or } \text{CollaborationCause}) \text{ and } ((\text{'has coordination strategy'} \text{ some } \text{CoordinationStrategy}) \text{ or } (\text{'has collaboration strategy'} \text{ some } \text{CollaborationStrategy}) \text{ or } (\text{'has congruence strategy'} \text{ some } \text{CongruenceStrategy}) \text{ or } (\text{'has communication strategy'} \text{ some } \text{CommunicationStrategy}) \text{ or } (\text{'has administrative preventive strategy'} \text{ some } \text{AdministrativePreventiveStrategy}))$
A3	A Cause linked to a specific Socio-technical Factor produces one or more Effects that impact one or more Socio-technical Factors.	$(\text{AdministrativeEffect} \sqcup \text{GroupEffect} \sqcup \text{IndividualEffect} \sqcup \text{ProjectManagementEffect} \sqcup \text{TechnicalEffect}) \sqsubseteq (\exists (\text{generatesEffect})^- . \text{CoordinationCause} \sqcup \exists (\text{generatesEffect})^- . \text{CommunicationCause} \sqcup \exists (\text{generatesEffect})^- . \text{CongruenceCause} \sqcup \exists (\text{generatesEffect})^- . \text{CollaborationCause} \sqcup \exists (\text{generatesEffect})^- . \text{AdministrativeCause})$	$(\text{AdministrativeEffect} \text{ or } \text{GroupEffect} \text{ or } \text{IndividualEffect} \text{ or } \text{ProjectManagementEffect} \text{ or } \text{TechnicalEffect}) \text{ and } (\text{inverse 'generates effect'} \text{ some } (\text{CoordinationCause} \text{ or } \text{CommunicationCause} \text{ or } \text{CongruenceCause} \text{ or } \text{CollaborationCause} \text{ or } \text{'Administrative cause'}))$
A4	Every Effect of social debt that impacts a given Socio-Technical Factor is mitigated by one or more Corrective Strategies that are applicable to that same factor.	$(\text{AdministrativeEffect} \sqcup \text{GroupEffect} \sqcup \text{IndividualEffect} \sqcup \text{ProjectManagementEffect} \sqcup \text{TechnicalEffect}) \sqsubseteq (\exists \text{hasAdministrativeStrategy.AdministrativeStrategy} \sqcup \exists \text{hasGroupStrategy.GroupStrategy} \sqcup \exists \text{hasIndividualStrategy.IndividualStrategy} \sqcup \exists \text{hasProjectManagementStrategy.ProjectManagementStrategy} \sqcup \exists \text{hasTechnicalStrategy.TechnicalStrategy})$	$(\text{AdministrativeEffect} \text{ or } \text{GroupEffect} \text{ or } \text{IndividualEffect} \text{ or } \text{ProjectManagementEffect} \text{ or } \text{TechnicalEffect}) \text{ and } ((\text{'has administrative strategy'} \text{ some } \text{AdministrativeStrategy}) \text{ or } (\text{'has group strategy'} \text{ some } \text{GroupStrategy}) \text{ or } (\text{'has individual strategy'} \text{ some } \text{IndividualStrategy}) \text{ or } (\text{'has project management strategy'} \text{ some } \text{ProjectManagementStrategy}) \text{ or } (\text{'has technical strategy'} \text{ some } \text{TechnicalStrategy}))$
A5	A specific Community Smell may generate one or more negative Effects that impact (at least one of) the Team Members, the Organization, Software Quality, or the Development Team.	$(\text{CoordinationCause} \sqcup \text{CommunicationCause} \sqcup \text{CongruenceCause} \sqcup \text{CollaborationCause} \sqcup \text{AdministrativeCause}) \sqsubseteq (\exists \text{causeCommunitySmell .xsd:string} \sqcap \exists \text{generatesEffect} . (\text{AdministrativeEffect} \sqcup \text{GroupEffect} \sqcup \text{IndividualEffect} \sqcup \text{ProjectManagementEffect} \sqcup \text{TechnicalEffect}) \sqcap (\exists \text{isAffectedByCause} . \text{Group} \sqcup \exists (\text{isAssociatedWithGroup})^- . \text{Group} \sqcup \exists (\text{hasCause})^- . \text{Organization}) \sqcap \exists \text{isLinkedToPerson} . \text{Person})$	$(\text{CoordinationCause} \text{ or } \text{CommunicationCause} \text{ or } \text{CongruenceCause} \text{ or } \text{CollaborationCause} \text{ or } \text{'Administrative cause'}) \text{ and } (\text{'Cause Community Smell'} \text{ some } \text{xsd:string}) \text{ and } (\text{'generates effect'} \text{ some } (\text{AdministrativeEffect} \text{ or } \text{GroupEffect} \text{ or } \text{IndividualEffect} \text{ or } \text{ProjectManagementEffect} \text{ or } \text{TechnicalEffect})) \text{ and } ((\text{'is affected by cause'} \text{ some } \text{Group}) \text{ or } (\text{inverse 'is associated with group'} \text{ some } \text{Group}) \text{ or } (\text{inverse 'has cause'} \text{ some } \text{Organization})) \text{ and } (\text{'is linked to person'} \text{ some } \text{Person})$
A6	An Indicator allows the detection of at least one specific Cause of Social Debt.	$\text{Indicator} \sqsubseteq \exists \text{indicatesCause} . \text{Cause}$	$\text{Indicator} \text{ and } (\text{indicatesCause} \text{ some } \text{Cause})$
A7	A Metric quantifies the impact of a Cause of social debt.	$\text{Metric} \sqsubseteq \exists \text{measuresCause} . \text{Cause}$	$\text{Metric} \text{ and } (\text{measuresCause} \text{ some } \text{Cause})$